

Polymetallic Complexes. Part-XXXIV. Complexes of Cobalt-, Nickel-, Copper-, Zinc-, Cadmium- and Mercury(II) with Chelating Azo Dye Ligands, 1,3-Bis[(5'-(1'-formyl-2'-hydroxyphenyl)azo)benzene and 1,3-Bis[5'-(1'-carboxyphenyl-2'-hydroxyphenyl)azo]benzene

BIPIN B MAHAPATRA*, SAMBHU P. PRADHAN and SUKHENDU K. KAR

Post-Graduate Department of Chemistry, G. M. College, Sambalpur-768 004

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Study of polymetallic complexes containing polydentate mono-azo and bis-azo dyes as ligands are of recent interest¹. So it was thought worthwhile to synthesise and characterise new bis-azo dyes having OOOO donor atoms and their metal complexes with some metal ions.

Results and Discussion

The complexes (Table 1) have the compositions $[M_2L_2.4H_2O][M'L_2]$, $[M_2L.8H_2O]$ and $[M_2L.4H_2O]$, where $M(II) = Co, Ni, Cu$; $M'(II) = Zn, Cd, Hg$; $LH_2 = 1,3$ -bis[5'-(1'-formyl-2'-hydroxyphenyl)-azo]benzene; $L'H_4 = 1,3$ -bis[5'-(1'-carboxyl-2'-hydroxyphenyl)azo]benzene. The complexes are stable at room temperature, amorphous in nature having high melting points and insoluble in common organic solvents but sparingly soluble in DMF. Non-electrolytic nature of the complexes is indicated from the low Λ_M values (4.5 – $5.8 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$).

The ir spectra of the ligands and their metal complexes are quite informative. In the spectra of the ligands, the bands at ca 3420 cm^{-1} (OH) lowered due to intramolecular O–H...O hydrogen bonding. The absence of this band in the metal chelates indicates the deprotonation of the phenolic OH groups and bonding of oxygen atom to the metal ions. The bands appearing at 1606 (LH_2) and 1608 cm^{-1} ($L'H_4$) assigned

to $\nu_{N=N}$ vibration, remain unaltered in the metal complexes showing non-coordination of azo nitrogen atoms to the metal ions². The band at 1640 cm^{-1} (LH_2) attributed to $\nu_{C=O}$ vibration shifted to 1622 – 1634 cm^{-1} in the metal complexes indicating the coordination of carbonyl oxygen atoms to the metal ions. The bands at 1506 (LH_2) and 1476 cm^{-1} ($L'H_4$) can be ascribed to phenolic ν_{C-O} vibration. The bathochromic shift of ca 35 cm^{-1} in the complexes of the former ligand and ca 15 – 25 cm^{-1} in the complexes of the latter ligand, indicates the bonding of both the azo dyes to the metal ions through the phenolic oxygen atoms³. A strong absorption at 1705 cm^{-1} ($L'H_4$) assigned to $\nu_{C=O}$ of free COO^- group⁴ shifted in all the complexes, indicating the absence of the free COOH groups⁵. The ν_{as} and ν_s vibrations of the COO^- group appearing at 1545 and 1310 cm^{-1} respectively ($\Delta\nu = 235 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) indicate that carboxylate group acts as unidentate coordinating agent⁶. In case of all the complexes except zinc, cadmium and mercury with the ligand LH_2 , the presence of coordinated water molecules is indicated by the appearance of a broad band at 3350 – 3450 cm^{-1} and a sharp band at ca 840 cm^{-1} , attributed to OH stretching and rocking vibrations respectively⁷. The evidence of bonding of oxygen atoms of the ligands to the metal ions is tentatively proved by the appearance of bands at ca 425 cm^{-1} assignable to ν_{M-O} vibration⁸.

In the electronic spectra of the Co^{II} complexes, four bands are observed at ca 8 795, 18 220, 21 970 and 32 150 cm^{-1} , assignable to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), $\rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ (ν_2), $\rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3) and CT transition respectively. The ligand

signable to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transitions in a distorted octahedral geometry¹¹.

The polycrystalline esr spectra of the complexes $[\text{Cu}_2\text{L}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ and $[\text{CuL}'(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8]$ have been recorded at X-band. The g_{II} and g_{I} values of these complexes have been calculated to be 2.261, 2.161 and 2.145, 2.062 respectively, using Kneubuhl's method¹². Since in both the complexes the g_{II} values are less than 2.3, it shows that the complexes are largely covalent. From the shape of the spectrum, it is evident that the symmetry around the Cu^{II} ions in the unit cell is tetragonal (elongated octahedral)¹³. The axial symmetry parameter (G) for the complexes has been calculated using the formula,

$$G = \frac{g_{\text{II}} - 2}{g_{\text{I}} - 2}$$

and the values are found to be 1.67 and 2.33 respectively. It shows a strong exchange interactions among magnetically inequivalent Cu^{II} ions in the unit cell¹⁴. Sub-normal magnetic moments of the Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes can be ascribed to partial quenching of paramagnetism due to metal-metal interactions in adimeric structure¹⁵. The Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes are presumably dimeric tetrahedral on the basis of analytical, conductance, solubility tests, high melting points and spectral data.

Hence both the azo dyes act as doubly-bidentate ligands bonded through phenolic oxygen, carbonyl oxygen and carboxyl oxygen atoms. The most probable structure of the complexes is presented in Fig. 1.

M(II) = Co, Ni, Cu; X = H₂O
M(II) = Zn, Cd, Hg; X = nil
Fig 1

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND MAGNETIC MOMENT DATA OF THE LIGANDS AND COMPLEXES

Compd / (Colour)	Analysis% (Found/Calcd)				μ_{eff} B M
	M	C	H	N	
LH ₂ (Reddish brown)	-	64.2 (64.2)	3.5 3.7	14.5 14.9	-
L'H ₂ (Brown)	-	58.8 (59.1)	3.5 3.7	13.4 13.8	-
$[\text{Co}_2\text{L}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ (Brown)	12.2 (12.6)	51.1 51.4	3.2 3.4	5.3 5.9	2.90
$[\text{Ni}_2\text{L}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ (Green)	12.3 (12.5)	51.2 51.4	3.3 3.4	5.5 5.9	2.50
$[\text{Cu}_2\text{L}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ (Green)	13.2 (13.4)	50.4 50.9	3.1 3.3	5.2 5.9	1.20
$[\text{Zn}_2\text{L}_2]$ (Brown)	14.4 (14.9)	54.2 54.8	2.5 2.7	6.2 6.4	-
$[\text{Cd}_2\text{L}_2]$ (Buff)	22.8 (23.2)	49.1 49.5	2.2 2.4	5.2 5.7	-
$[\text{Hg}_2\text{L}_2]$ (Buff)	34.7 (35.0)	41.2 41.9	1.9 2.1	4.5 4.8	-
$[\text{Co}_2\text{L}'(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8]$ (Dark brown)	17.5 (17.6)	35.8 36.0	4.0 4.2	8.2 8.4	2.85
$[\text{Ni}_2\text{L}'(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8]$ (Brown)	17.2 (17.6)	35.7 36.0	4.0 4.2	8.1 8.4	2.40
$[\text{Cu}_2\text{L}'(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8]$ (Green)	18.5 (18.8)	35.2 35.5	3.9 4.1	8.1 8.4	1.25
$[\text{Zn}_2\text{L}'(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ (Brown)	21.2 (21.5)	39.4 39.5	3.1 3.3	9.0 9.2	-
$[\text{Cd}_2\text{L}'(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ (Grey)	31.5 (32.0)	33.7 34.2	2.4 2.8	7.3 7.9	-
$[\text{Hg}_2\text{L}'(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ (Light brown)	45.2 (45.7)	27.1 27.3	2.1 2.2	5.8 6.3	-

*LH₂ = 1,3-bis[5'-(1'-formyl-2'-hydroxyphenyl)azo]benzene,
L'H₄ = 1,3-bis[5'-(1'-carboxy-2'-hydroxyphenyl)azo]benzene

field parameters like Dq , B , β_{35} , ν_2/ν_1 and σ (Table 2) suggest an octahedral stereochemistry for the complexes⁹. The Ni^{II} complexes show four bands at 11 820, 18 535, 27 845 and 31 390 cm^{-1} , attributable to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), $\rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2) $\rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3) and CT bands respectively. The values of ligand field parameters suggest an octahedral geometry around the metal ions¹⁰. The Cu^{II} complexes show broad asymmetric ligand field bands at 13 360–15 785 cm^{-1} with the maxima at ca 14 440 cm^{-1} , as-

TABLE 2—SPECTRAL PARAMETERS OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd.	λ_{\max} cm ⁻¹	Dq cm ⁻¹	B cm ⁻¹	β_{35}	ν_2/ν_1	σ
[Co ₂ L ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄]	8 795 18 220 21 970 32 150	942	873.6	0.899	2.07	11.23
[Co ₂ L'(H ₂ O) ₈]	8 770 18 185 21 880 32 225	941	917.0	0.944	2.07	5.95
[Ni ₂ L ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄]	11 820 18 535 27 845 31 390	1 182	728.0	0.6993	1.56	43.00
[Ni ₂ L'(H ₂ O) ₈]	11 805 18 544 27 795 31 410	1 180	728.2	0.6995	1.57	42.95

Experimental

All the chemicals are of A.R. grade. The bis-azo dyes were synthesised by the usual method. The complexes were prepared by refluxing (0.5 h) a mixture of the ethanolic solution of metal(II) chloride with the ligand in EtOH in 1 : 1 molar ratio. On cooling, liquor ammonia was added dropwise with stirring and the resulting metal complex was washed with ethanol, ether and dried under reduced pressure.

The metal, C, H and N were determined by standard methods. Conductance of the complexes was measured in 10⁻³ M dimethylformamide. Magnetic susceptibility was measured at room temperature using a Gouy balance. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 398 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra (in 10⁻² M DMF) on a Hilger and Wat Uvispeck spectrophotometer and esr

spectra on a Varian E-4 ESR spectrometer at room temperature.

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